

Fuzzware Configuration Tool Documentation

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Disclaimer

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1 Description

The configuration tool is meant to improve the user-friendliness of setting up the Fuzzware configuration file. It comes with functionality for automatically creating a configuration for the nRF52 family of devices, modifying memory regions, creating static UICR and FICR binaries, loading function symbols, testing the configuration, and more. While the tool is mainly developed for the nRF52 family, it can also be used as a helper script for modifying configurations created for other devices.

This document features a walkthrough of how to use the script, and an insight into the functionalities it provides. Section 3 contains a flowchart of the script. Section 4 features a guide on how to start the script. Section 5 goes through the functionalities provided by the tool. Section 6 notes some of the limitations with the configuration tool. Section 7 contains examples of use cases. Section 8 contains a list of required utilities for running the setup. Lastly, the appendix chapter features tips for optimizing fuzzer performance and coverage, setting up Fuzzware, and tips on analyzing results.

1.1 Supported Devices

The automatic configuration of memory map works for the following devices:

- nRF52840

- nRF52832
- nRF52810
- nRF52811
- nRF52820
- nRF52833

2 Motivation

While embedded fuzzing has long been shown to be an effective vulnerability discovery technique, its level of user friendliness can be argued. There are many open source fuzzers available, tailored for different targets and architectures.

Fuzzware is a fuzzing tool that can be used to inject unexpected MMIO reads in an emulated environment of embedded devices. While it has shown to be effective in identifying zero days, it is also noted to be difficult to configure for testing SoC's, and often requires hours/days of trial and error before finding a configuration that works for their target. This tool was therefore developed to aid users in setting up, and optimizing the Fuzzware configuration file.

3 Flowchart

Figure 1: Flowchart of the configuration tool

4 Startup Behavior

Upon execution, the script expects two arguments: a target directory and the firmware binary filename.

```
$ python3 configuration_tool.py targets/nrf my_firmware.bin
```

The target directory is the folder which contains the binary, and where the configuration will be put. The firmware binary is the firmware file that will be emulated and fuzzed, the entry point of the emulation. In addition to this, there are three flags that can be used as arguments:

- `--auto`: Automatically writes a configuration file to target directory.
- `--run`: Automatically starts a fuzzing session.
- `--elf ELF_PATH`: Automatically parses symbols from a provided elf path, then creates handlers for skipping delay functions that follow a certain pattern (highly recommended for NSDK firmware).

After launching the script, the user can choose whether to:

1. Generate new configuration.
2. Load configuration from target folder.
3. Load configuration from custom path.

If the user chooses to generate a new configuration, the script will retrieve the size of the flash, and perform a basic check to see if the IVT is located at 0x0. If the check fails, the user will be prompted to insert an offset to IVT. Then, the script initializes a memory map based on the memory layout of nRF52840, the binary size, and the IVT offset.

If the user instead chooses to load an existing configuration, the script will parse the existing configuration file and load the memory map along with models.

Running the script with all flags can be executed through the following command-line:

```
$ python3 configuration_tool.py ../target_dir target.bin --run -auto --elf target.elf
```

5 Functionality

5.1 Memory Map Configuration

Users can print, add, remove, and modify memory regions. Each region includes:

- Name.
- Start Address.
- Size.
- Permissions.
- Optional file, IVT offset, and entry point (only relevant if there are more than two binaries, and for the memory section which is the entry point).

5.2 Symbol Retrieval

Users can load symbols that map addresses to symbols, through three input sources:

1. Raw text file (format: `<address>: <symbol>`)
2. Existing configuration file.
3. ELF file via `readelf`

Importing symbols from an existing configuration file can be useful if the user has already used Fuzzware `genconfig` to generate a configuration, which potentially already contains symbols if done from an ELF file.

5.3 MMIO Model Configuration

Users can add constants, passthroughs, and sets at specified combinations of memory addresses and program counters.

- Constant: Makes the fuzzer read a specified value from specified MMIO register at specified location.
- Set: Similar to constant, but allows the fuzzer to select from a predefined set of values.
- Passthrough: Treats an MMIO address as normal memory, allowing both reads and writes.

MMIO models are particularly useful for skipping over hardware-dependent stalls, suppressing noise from non-influential reads, or crafting deterministic behaviors that help the fuzzer explore deeper, more meaningful code paths.

5.4 Interrupt Model Configuration

Users can choose to add and remove predefined types of interrupt models to the configuration, based on examples from Fuzzware target configuration README. The following models are included in the script:

- Default: Fuzzware chooses interrupt from the ones enabled and performs in roundrobin fashion every 1000 ticks.
- Fuzzer chosen tick based: Interrupts are choosen in a fuzzed fashion, between user specified amount of ticks.
- Fuzzer chosen on address: Interrupts are fuzzed when specific address or symbol is reached during emulation.
- Fixed interrupt tick based: A user chosen interrupt is called every user specified amount of ticks.
- Fixed interrupt address based: A user chosen interrupt is called every time an address or symbol is passed.
- Fully fuzzed: Interrupts are chosen by fuzzer at a random tick interval.

5.5 Boot Requirements

Allows users to specify:

- Addresses or symbols that must be passed for a successful boot
- Addresses or symbols that must be avoided for a successful boot

For this the work, the user must also choose a Target address/symbol that symbolizes a successful boot, based on whether the functions specified required or avoided were passed.

These are useful to maximize the time that the fuzzer is spending in valuable regions, can be extra valuable for binaries with complex boot process with MMIO reads.

5.6 SoftDevice Filtering

Fuzzing NSDK firmware resulted in spending a lot of time in the Softdevice bootloader. To bypass this, the user can enable SoftDevice Filtering/Magic that automatically injects constants at certain UICR reads in the Softdevice.

Note: This has only been tested on firmware developed with NSDK 15.3. It will not work on Zephyr SDK firmware, since it has a different booting process.

5.7 FICR/UICR Loader

Users can choose to make the fuzzer treat FICR and UICR regions as regular memory space instead of as an MMIO region. This is done by either:

1. Loading a hexdump containing FICR/UICR content (in big endian).
2. Creating a hexdump of FICR/UICR content, through nrfjprog and a USB connected device.

The hexdump is then used to create a binary file that contains the dumped memory content, which is put in the target directory. The configuration is automatically changed to treat the region/regions as regular memory space instead of MMIO.

This feature can be useful for reducing unnecessary fuzzing overhead. Since FICR contains factory-programmed, read-only values, treating it as a fuzzable region may result in many unproductive reads that do not affect control flow. It also enables starting a fuzzing session from a certain state of UICR/FICR content.

Note: Creating a binary file of FICR content from a connected chip requires running this option on the host system, and not within the Docker environment: Run script on host → create FICR binary from chip → save configuration → start the Docker environment → run script → start fuzzing session.

5.8 Handlers

The user can set up handlers for overwriting instructions with patches, based on provided address / symbol, and a handler. These can be useful in delay functions, or functions that does operation uninteresting to test in the fuzzing session.

Some example handlers include:

- native.inline_asm_006F: Patches address with NOP (patches 2 bytes).
- native.inline_asm_7047: Patches specified address with bx lr (patches 2 bytes)
- native.inline_return_0x0: Branches to pointer in link register, returning 0 (patches 8 bytes).
- native.inline_return_0x1: Branches to pointer in link register, returning 1 (patches 8 bytes).

Fuzzware also supports the use of python hooks as handlers, due to complexity this is not included in this script. For more on this, see Fuzzware documentation on their github page.

5.9 Exit At

The user can utilize Fuzzwares Exit At configuration option to set addresses / symbols, which makes fuzzer exit a execution path at a specified location.

This can be useful if the user want to disregard certain execution paths from testing.

5.10 Saving

Users can save the active configuration, writing it as config.yml inside target directory. If the file already exists, the old one is renamed to config_old.yml.

5.11 Testing Configuration

Users can test the configuration that is open in the script. This feature uses Fuzzware emu with -v (verbose), -t(functions) and -M arguments, and checks whether Fuzzware emu runs as expected or whether it exits due to invalid configuration. Important to note is that it only tests whether the fuzzer runs, and not whether it leads to interesting code.

Before running the emulation command, the script saves a temporary configuration to the target directory as config.yml and moves existing configuration to config_tmp_mv.yml. After the test is finished the temporary config is removed and the moved file is moved back as config.yml.

5.12 Running Fuzzing Session

Users can start the Fuzzware pipeline directly from script, with specified flags for how long to run the pipeline, whether to use afl++ (an improved version of the AFL fuzzing harness), and how many cores of the CPU to utilize. The function verifies that the pipeline starts and outputs live data from the session.

Additionally, the user gets the option to skip skip-afl-cpufreq. This is a threshold variable used to limit CPU usage. In our testing, we chose to skip the threshold, to provide as much computing power as possible to the fuzzer. If the user instead wants to set a threshold, this must be done manually.

Before running the pipeline command, the script saves a temporary configuration to the target directory as config.yml and moves existing configuration to config_tmp_mv.yml. After the session is finished. the temporary config is removed and the moved file is moved back as config.yml.

For further information about understanding the result, see our documentation on the crash analysis tool and Fuzzware's own documentation.

6 Limitations

As the script is centered on user-friendly and easy to setup fuzzing, some capabilities of Fuzzware were left out of scope. One of these functionalities is the ability to create custom hooks through python that the emulation can initiate at specified timings or locations.

For more information about manual additions of adding custom hooks, see Fuzzware's github page.

Another limitation is that the configuration tool is unable to validate whether the fuzzer reaches good coverage or not. This requires manual analysis. Similarly, crashes also required manual analysis for finding what caused the crash. In our experience, Fuzzing is a continuous

process of running sessions, analyzing results, and adding optimizations based on the results to improve coverage.

7 Usage Examples

7.1 nRF52, NSDK, Quick

```
$ python3 configuration_tool.py targets/nrf my_firmware.bin --auto
--run
```

7.2 nRF52, NSDK, SoftDevice Filtering

```
$ python3 configuration_tool.py targets/nrf my_firmware.bin

#####File Retrieval#####

Found binary: ../testing/test.bin
Do you want to load an existing config, or generate a new based on nRF52840 template?

0. Exit
1. Generate a new config
2. Load from ../testing directory
3. Load from custom pathEnter choice: 1

#####IVT and Flash Size Retrieval##### ...
#####Populating Memory Map##### ...
#####Config Menu#####

1. Print Memory Map
2. Modify Memory Map
3. Skip Softdevice Noise

4. Add Symbols
5. Load UICR/FICR preset file
6. Modify BOOT requirements
7. Modify MMIO models
8. Modify Interrupt Config
9. Save config
10. Test Configuration
11. Run
0. Exit
Enter menu choice: 3

#####Softdevice Magic#####

0. Exit
1. Add Magic
2. Remove Existing
Enter menu choice: 1
```

```
#####Config Menu#####
```

1. Print Memory Map
2. Modify Memory Map
3. Skip Softdevice Noise
4. Add Symbols
5. Load UICR/FICR preset file
6. Modify BOOT requirements
7. Modify MMIO models
8. Modify Interrupt Config
9. Save config
10. Test Configuration
11. Run
0. Exit

```
Enter menu choice: 11
```

7.3 nRF52, NSDK, Static FICR from Device

```
$ python3 configuration_tool.py targets/nrf my_firmware.bin ...
```

```
#####Config Menu#####
```

Note, the configuration will not be saved unless explicitly choosing the save option.

1. Print Memory Map
2. Modify Memory Map
3. Skip Softdevice Noise
4. Add Symbols
5. Load UICR/FICR preset file
6. Modify BOOT requirements
7. Modify MMIO models
8. Modify Interrupt Config
9. Modify Return Handlers

- 10. Modify Exit At Model
- 11. Save config
- 12. Test Fuzzing Configuration
- 13. Start Fuzzing Session

0. Exit

Enter menu choice: 5

#####Load FICR/UICR preset##### ...

- 0. Exit
- 1. Load FICR from .bin
- 2. Create FICR binary from chip
- 3. Remove FICR binary

- 6. Load UICR from .bin
- 7. Create UICR binary from chip
- 8. Remove UICR binary

Enter menu choice: 2

#####Generate FICR Binary#####

Note, this requires nrfjprog, and a readable chip connected. Temporary dump saved to tmp_FICR.hex

Saved memory content to hexstream, removing tmp file...

Successfully wrote hex stream to ../testing/FICR.bin..

Success...FICR config updated

#####Config Menu#####

Note, the configuration will not be saved unless explicitly choosing the save option.

- 1. Print Memory Map
- 2. Modify Memory Map
- 3. Skip Softdevice Noise
- 4. Add Symbols
- 5. Load UICR/FICR preset file
- 6. Modify BOOT requirements
- 7. Modify MMIO models
- 8. Modify Interrupt Config
- 9. Modify Return Handlers
- 10. Modify Exit At Model

- 11. Save config

- 12. Test Fuzzing Configuration
- 13. Start Fuzzing Session

0. Exit

Enter menu choice: 1

...

#####Memory Map##### ...

memory_map:

FLASH:

base_addr: 0x0 size: 0x413dc

permissions: r-x is_entry: True

ivt_offset: 0x0 file: test.bin FICR:

base_addr: 0x10000000 size:

0x1000 permissions: r-file:

FICR.bin

mmio_UICR:

base_addr: 0x10001000 size:

0x1000 permissions: rwSRAM:

base_addr: 0x20000000 size:

0x40000 permissions: rw-

mmio_APB:

base_addr: 0x40000000 size:

0x10000000 permissions: rw-

mmio_AHB:

base_addr: 0x50000000 size:

0x10000000 permissions: rwNVIC:

base_addr: 0xe0000000 size:

0x10000000 permissions:

rwIRQ_RET: base_addr: 0xffff000

size: 0x1000 permissions: --x ...

7.4 nRF52, Elf Flag

```
$ python3 configuration_tool.py ../testing/test.bin --elf test.elf #####File Retrieval##### ...
```

```
Found binary file: ../testing/test.bin Reading symbols from elf file.
```

```
...
```

```
#####Config Menu#####
```

Note, the configuration will not be saved unless explicitly choosing the save option.

1. Print Memory Map
2. Modify Memory Map
3. Skip Softdevice Noise
4. Add Symbols
5. Load UICR/FICR preset file
6. Modify BOOT requirements
7. Modify MMIO models
8. Modify Interrupt Config
9. Modify Return Handlers
10. Modify Exit At Model
11. Save config
12. Test Fuzzing Configuration
13. Start Fuzzing Session

0. Exit

Enter menu choice: 4

```
#####Symbol Loader#####
```

Symbols can be added to simplify analysis and provide mapping between addresses and function names.

Currently loaded symbols 1336 ...

8 Dependencies

- Python 3
- nrfjprog: Only if creating static FICR/UICR binaries.
- Fuzzware: If user tests, or runs pipeline directly from configuration.
- readelf: If user retrieves symbols from elf file.
- pyyaml: If user reads .yml file during startup.

A Analyzing Crashes

Based on our experiences with Fuzzware, understanding the root of crashes is often timeconsuming, and requires manual analysis.

The most important tool to understanding crashes is the Fuzzware replay command, which allows users to replay traces that led to a crash, documenting addresses visited, reads, and writes.

To simplify the process of replaying crashes, we created a small helper script that:

1. Gathers crash contexts (using Fuzzware `genstat crashcontexts`)
2. Parses crash contexts and provides them with id numbers.
3. Gives the ability to replay a crash through choosing a bucket id, and a trace path from the bucket.
4. Saves the output of the replay to a `.txt` file.

Some common patterns to look for in fuzzwares replay output includes:

As Fuzzware fuzzes MMIO reads, it is useful to search for patterns in the replay output that matches the firmware's MMIO memory regions (for instance addresses with the pattern `0x400XXXXX`, `0x500XXXXX`, or other device specific peripheral ranges). A good understanding of memory layout, address spaces, hexadecimal notation, and common instruction patterns can significantly aid in interpreting the output and identifying the root cause of crashes.

Repeating hex values such as `0x47474747` are likely to stem from a fuzzed input. If these can be found in the stack trace, it is possible that the value has been used as a variable in the emulation. If the crash seems to be rooted in such an input, it could mean that inputs is not being properly validated before it is used. If the pattern is found in a invalid read/write crash, it could mean that a fuzzed input was retrieved from the stack, potentially having overwritten the expected value. Repeating occurrences of a single, or few addresses could means that the fuzzer got stuck in a loop. If the loop is waiting for an event, the user should consider adding a manual interrupt model at that address. If it stems from delay functionality, the user should consider patching the starting address of the address with a `bx lr`.

Furthermore, we found it useful to utilize the reverse engineering tool *Ghidra* to get a visual representation of code blocks visited in the replay output.

B Improving Coverage and Decreasing False Positives

While the configuration tool creates a configuration that work for nRF52840 devices, it does not guarantee strong code coverage.

In our experience, fuzzing is a continues process of running test, assessing results, and improving configuration (setting patches, adding MMIO models, etc). Improving the configuration means reducing time that the fuzzer spends in unwanted states (such as in delays, and in wait for semaphores), enabling both faster execution, and better coverage.

The following are some tips for improving coverage and reducing false positive crashes that were utilized during our experiments:

- Skip Delays: Delay loops are generally unwanted as it can take up much execution time. We mainly relied on patching calls to delays with NOP instructions, which improved

execution speed, and reduced false positive (caused by interrupts during delays) crashes significantly.

- Set Manual Interrupts: Adding interrupt models on functions that are loops waiting for events can greatly improve execution speed.
- Avoid FPU instructions: Fuzzware does not support FPU instructions such as `vpush`. It is therefore recommended to compile binaries using flags that avoids them. Or try to patch over calls to functions that use them.
- Add a Boot Model: When bootloaders are present, adding a boot model that symbolically marks a successful boot can help skip redundant bootloader execution in later fuzzing runs. Initially, it may be useful to fuzz the bootloader itself to discover any low-level issues. However, once its behavior is understood or deemed out of scope, focus can shift to the main application. This can be achieved by setting the main function as the boot target and configuring the reset handler as a required visited address.

While patching is a powerful tool for improving coverage, it must be done with care to preserve correct control flow. For example, inserting a `bx lr` patch in the middle of a function (before `pop`), can corrupt the stack and cause unintended behavior.

C Coverage Comparer

An additional script created is a coverage comparer (`coverage_compare.py`), which can be used to create diagrams of code blocks visited (y axis) and execution time (x axis). The script takes in a list of pipeline logs, which is output to

target/Fuzzware-project/logs/pipeline.log during fuzzing sessions. An example of an output is provided in figure TODO.

D Setting up fuzzing environment

D.1 Preparing Linux system

The linux distribution generally recommended for running fuzzware is currently Ubuntu 22.04. Ubuntu is typically run either:

- As the operating system on a physical computer, or
- In a virtual machine (VM)

D.1.1 On physical machine

1. Download the Ubuntu image and create a bootable USB drive containing the image. (Ubuntu 22.04, and other Ubuntu versions can be downloaded from the Ubuntu website: <https://releases.ubuntu.com/>)
2. Boot from the USB drive by starting up the computer with the bootable USB drive inserted. (this may require first changing the BIOS/UEFI settings such that USB boot has higher priority than internal storage boot)

3. Complete the Ubuntu installation procedure, entering appropriate choices when prompted.

D.1.2 On virtual machine

Setting up a virtual Ubuntu machine in a hypervisor such as VMware or VirtualBox will not be covered in detail here, but it typically involves downloading a suitable image, ensuring appropriate settings, and then installing/running the Ubuntu OS on the VM.

Another common tool for running virtual Linux machines is Windows Subsystem for Linux (WSL), which can be set up with the following general procedure:

1. Ensure virtualization is enabled
2. Open PowerShell (as administrator) and run the WSL install command:

```
wsl --install
```

When the install completes, reboot the computer.

3. To find Ubuntu 22.04, go to Windows Store and search for "Ubuntu 22.04". Click the button to get/install Ubuntu 22.04, and enter a user name and password when prompted.

A WSL instance with Ubuntu 22.04 should now be up and running. Consult with available WSL tutorials for more advanced use (e.g. creating multiple WSL instances, taking backups of images, etc.). More WSL installation guidance can also be found at <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/wsl/install>

D.2 Cloning repository

After setting up a physical or virtual Ubuntu machine, the next step is to clone the fuzzware repository and prepare the system for running fuzzware. This guideline shows how to clone SINTEF's NEMECYS-specific repository which is based on fuzzware and contains additional tools (such as the configuration script) meant to make fuzzware easier to use. The repository can be cloned with the following command:

```
git clone --recursive https://gitlab.sintef.no/nemecys-public/aurora-fuzzware.git
```

The `--recursive` flag ensures that the necessary submodules are loaded/initialized. (If the repository is cloned non-recursively, make sure to run `update.sh` before running `build_docker.sh` or `install_local.sh`.)

D.3 Setting up fuzzware

With the repository cloned, fuzzware can either be installed locally, or run in a container using Docker. We have mainly used the containerized approach when developing NEMECYS-specific scripts for fuzzing.

D.3.1 Running fuzzware with Docker

Setting up Docker is quite straightforward (assuming a fresh install of Ubuntu), using the script `ubuntu_install_docker.sh` in the fuzzware repository. Go to the root of the cloned repository and run the following command:

```
./ubuntu_install_docker.sh
```

Press enter if prompted to "Press [ENTER] to continue". When the install has completed, add `$USER` to the docker group (this is necessary for the `build_docker.sh` script to run successfully):

```
sudo usermod -aG docker $USER
```

For the changes to take effect, either log out and log in, or run the command:

```
newgrp docker
```

From the root of the fuzzware repository, the `build_docker.sh` script can now be run:

```
./build_docker.sh
```

This script should prepare a Docker image with all the necessary content to run fuzzware sessions. To launch a fuzzing container, use the `run_docker.sh` script:

```
./run_docker.sh
```

This will run a Docker container, and map all the contents of the examples folder to the Docker container. All content in the examples folder should now be available inside the container, such that the configuration and fuzzing procedures described in Chapter 4 can be performed. Relevant files produced during fuzzing sessions should automatically be stored on the host, such that they are not lost when exiting the container.

D.3.2 Local installation of fuzzware

If, for some reason, a local install of fuzzware (without the use of Docker) is preferred, the following instructions can be followed to set up a local build. These guidelines are not necessarily the "only" or "best" way to prepare Ubuntu for local installation of fuzzware, but they have led to successful installation in our experiments. The list of necessary packages is based on various online guidelines, and may contain some tools which are not strictly necessary.

Before installing packages, update the system:

```
sudo apt update && sudo apt upgrade -y
```

Then, install necessary packages:

```
sudo apt install -y \ build-essential \
  git \ cmake \ clang \ llvm-11 \
  llvm-11-dev \ unzip \
  automake \ autoconf \ libtool \
  \ pkg-config \ gcc-arm-none-
  eabi \ redis-server \ python3 \
```

```
python3-pip \ python3-venv \  
gcc-10-plugin-dev \ tmux
```

Additionally, the following pip package should be installed:

```
python3 -m pip install --user virtualenvwrapper
```

Now that these packages are installed, some additions need to be made to the `.bashrc` file, to enable the system to locate and use all the tools:

```
sudo nano ~/.bashrc
```

Add the following at the end of `.bashrc`:

```
export LLVM_CONFIG=/usr/bin/llvm-config-11 export  
WORKON_HOME=$HOME/.virtualenvs export  
VIRTUALENVWRAPPER_PYTHON=/usr/bin/python3 export  
PATH=$HOME/.local/bin:$PATH source  
~/.local/bin/virtualenvwrapper.sh
```

Lastly, after updating `.bashrc`, these changes need to be "applied":

```
source ~/.bashrc
```

The system should now be ready to run the script for local installation of fuzzware. Navigate to the root of the fuzzware repository and run the script:

```
./install_local.sh
```

When the script has run and completed, fuzzware commands can be run as long as the fuzzware environment is activated. To activate the environment, run the following command:

```
workon fuzzware
```

A "(fuzzware)" prefix should now be added in the terminal, indicating that the fuzzware environment is active. Fuzzware commands can now be run. To deactivate the fuzzware environment, run the command deactivate.